

SAMARKAND WATER SUPPLY: CHUPANATA WELL FIELD CCTV INSPECTION

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Abstract: *Samarkand is the second largest city in Uzbekistan and regional administrative center with almost one million population. Also, it is one of the ancient and very important cultural and historical UNESCO cities in Uzbekistan. Touristic attractiveness, geographical location, cultural and administrative importance of the city gives to this region a great business and touristic opportunity. Wellbeing and comfort of inhabitants directly related to regularity on the water supply system. Samarkand’s water supply system works entirely at the expense of underground water. Quality and quantity indicators of the ground waters allow to use them in all sectors of economy. The main water intake facilities for Samarkand are Chupanata and Dagbit well fields (WF). There is a big number of water wells and they are under specific operational control. As a surface water Zaravshan river is the main source for the infiltration ground waters for Chupanata and Dagbit WFs. Water intake facilities are located 4-8 km away from the city and in the flood land of Zaravshan River. This article devoted to the proper water well operation and effective water production of Chupanata WF and water well diagnostics by using CCTV. Which gives a clear picture for the water well problems and decreasing their debit. Investigation results could be used for the water well rehabilitation and sustainable water resources management in the region.*

Key words: *Water wells, debit, well capacity, inspection, CCTV method, specific debit, water table, static and dynamic water table, rehabilitation, sustainable water management.*

Analysis. Methodology. Chupanata WF is located on the left bank of Zaravshan River on the first terrace above the food line land in 8 km to the North-East of Samarkand city and occupies an area of 110 hectares. The well field is very close to Katta Uzbek international highway. Actual elevation above sea level is 688 m and the slope of the ground surface from South-West to North-East is 0-0.5. According to geological structure, Chupanata WF is located in fertile land with layers of sand and gravel. In terms of geomorphological structure, the area belongs to piedmont plain adjacent to the Northern slope of Karatube mountain chain and consists of a thick layer of proluvial deposits of Middle Quaternary Age. The first layer of soils consists of earth and plant remains. Its thickness is 0.4 m. The second layer of soils is loamy sand with lentils and layers of clay loam of non-saline hard composition. The layer thickness is 4.5-5.5 m. The third layer of soils is gravel and pebble. The structure is changing according to the relief. The soils belong to the 1st category of subsiding. Ground water corrosiveness to steel is average. Water quality is good and could be recommended to deliver and distribute to the water consumers with chlorination only

Drinking water supplied to the centralized household water supply system of the city. Water intake facilities should comply with the requirements of State Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan O‘zDSt 950:2011 named “Drinking Water, Hygiene

Requirements and Quality Control”. According to the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan named Concerning Water and Water Use, the state control and monitoring are applied in water use and protection which provide quality and security of ground waters. Article 15 prohibits operation and commission of enterprises, structures and other facilities influencing water condition. Chapters 7 and 8 of the law regulate the order and terms for permitting use of water systems and especially emphasize use of irrigation channels in agriculture directly influencing formation of ground waters.

According to the Cabinet of Ministers, Republic of Uzbekistan decree No. 302 dated 26 August 2002, to the **Chupanata**, Kunduz, Karadarya and Damkhodja sections are given status of specially protected zones of Republican level where deposits of fresh ground waters are formed. According to the above decree, potentially environment unfriendly facilities should be under special control for rational use of fresh ground water resources and protecting them from contamination.

Samarkand receives approximately 300,000 m³/d from Chupanata and Dagbit as the group working wells WFs including other small water intake stations. However, Chupanata WF gives to the Samarkand city approximately 70% of water demand and it is the main water intake station in the region where work a big group of the water wells. According to geological structure, Samarkand is located in the fertile land. The structure is changing according to the relief. The ground water is usually found at the depth of 10-20 m. The ground water at the WFs is usually recharged by atmospheric precipitation, by Zaravshan river as well as by irrigation channels.

Approximately 90% of existing wells are operating. All water wells on the Chupanata WF are in different state depending on duration and condition of operation. Here are some analysis results of the WF location, water well operation and water production indicators.

Hydrogeological characteristics of the Chupanata WF.

Table 1.

Seismicity rate	8	Climatic category of the region	IV
Ground waters levels: maximum	2 m deep	Soil characteristics	Gravel and sand
Ground water corrosiveness	Non-corrosive	Soil subsiding	I category
Specified depth of freezing	0.3 m		

There are 52 wells at the Chupanata WF. 43 of them are operating. Presently 37 are used and 6 are clogged and stopped. It provides approximately 70% on the water demand for the Samarkand city. The exploitable volume of ground water in the area is usually recharged by precipitation, by Zaravshan River, as well as by two Karasu

irrigation channels. The proved amount of ground water exploitable volume in this location is 271500 m³/d according to category A and 117000 m³ /d according to Category C.

The static level of ground water is vary and it changes between 5-15 m, the dynamic level is changes depending water intake and pump capacity. Its mineralization reaches 0.5-0.7 g/l and its hardness is 5.5-7.0 mg-eq/l. Filtration coefficient in case of scattered disposition of wells is 85.1 m/d and 64.0 m/d in case of successive disposition.

Obtained/collected and summarized general data included in the table below:

Table 2

Name of the wells	Year of commission	Depth of the wells	Notes
No No 1-52	1965-1991	Between 45-70 m	Not proper operation; High risk of surface water penetration

Depending on duration and operational conditions, the wells of Chupanata WF are in different state. The design well discharge is 64.5 l/sec compared to specified discharge of 5-10 l/sec.m. The project for “Further development of Chupanata WF in Samarkand (second part)” done by Uzbekkommunloyiha 1993 y., stipulates monitoring investigations to inspect ground water contamination in surface aquifers, ground water level and temperature but we have not found this information. The depth of the wells is between 45 and 70 m. The wells are equipped with filters of T-16 and F1V type that are 21 m long. There is a possibility of contaminating ground water by the WF’s own transformers, toilets, and an emergency pond. Ground water can be also contaminated by neighbor facilities – Chupan-Ata electrical substations located in the South-West and in the second area of the sanitary protection zone; by Zaravshan collective enterprise, car service station, private houses in the South and in the West as well as agricultural lands and international highway.

Pic.1 Clogged well filter and gravel zone (left). Clean filter and gravel zone (right)

Pic.2 Clogged well filter and gravel zone (node A)

Theoretically water wells can get clogged by different reasons. On Chupanata WF they were clogged by salt deposits’ sedimentation, metal elements’ corrosion products and small pieces of the sand (from aquifer). Possible sources of Chupanata WF well filter and gravel zone clogging are: quality and aggressiveness of the ground

Pic. 3 Chupanata WF location scheme

waters (hardness, mineralization, metallic elements corrosion), operation regime (frequently and unimpededly stops and switching on) indicators, aging of the filters, environmental pollution products from the surface waters close industries neighboring householders around Chupanata WF. We investigate a real condition of the 43 water wells at the Chupanata WF (table 3). Results show a different reasons for the improper working and operation regime.

Among the analyzed wells 23 of them were recommended to clean or rehabilitate by different methods. Other 20 were decided to conservate or to tamponage.

Contamination Risk: According to geological structure, Chupanata WF is vulnerable to the penetration of surface and atmospheric water into the aquifer.

- 24 transformer substations with a capacity of 100 to 250 kW are used on the territory of Chupan-Ata WF for process needs. Their operation involves use of the transformer oil and creates a risk of oil products penetration into the ground water;
- Incorrect economic activity related to planting the territory within the first area of the sanitary protection zone;
- Karasu Canal used for irrigation of farmlands and flowing through the first area of the sanitary protection zone is a potential source of dangerous substances penetration into the ground water;
- The 2nd level pump station is a potential source of ground water contamination by oil and oil products as it is located in the first area of the sanitary protection zone;
- To drain the water from the reservoirs, there is an open unprotected emergency draining pond on the territory of the WF near the highway. It is a potential source of accumulation and penetration of oil products and other substances into the ground

water;

- Absence of centralized sewage and protected cesspits on the territory of Chupan-Ata WF and neighbor facilities results in direct penetration of dangerous pollutants (feces) into the aquifer;

- Around the territory of the WF there are electrical substations, mineral water

Pic 4. CCTV of the filter (well #13).

Pic 5. CCTV of the filter (well #35)

- and ice-cream plants, marble factory, private houses, highway and cultivated areas – sources of environmental pollution subject to special supervision.

Karasu River is flowing through the WFs sanitary protection zone. It is used for irrigation purposes and poses a great risk of agrochemical and other pollutants penetration into the ground water.

CCTV inspection and analysis. Tabl.2

ROW	WELL registration NUMBER	DRILLING DATE	Depth according to the well passport	Depth according to CCTV	Proposal
4	5	1965	40.5	16.32	To liquidate and build a new well
11	13	1976	35	22.66	To liquidate and build a new well
12	14	1976	35	34.3	To clean and rehabilitate
13	15	1976	35	24	To liquidate and build a new well
15	18	1976	35	44.62	To clean and rehabilitate
28	35	1987	37	53	To clean and rehabilitate
29	36	1987	35	19.19	To liquidate and build a new well
30	37	1987	40	48.34	To clean and rehabilitate
31	38	1987	35	15.6	To liquidate and build a new well
35	43	1988	40	23.19	To liquidate and build a new well
38	46	1990	37	28.61	To clean and rehabilitate
43	52	1991	35	26	To liquidate and build a new well

The risk of surface pollutants penetration into the aquifer if the design filtration coefficient is 64 m/d is 2-2.5 hours.

It should be noted that high amplitude of Zaravshan River water level fluctuation

results in flow direction change of the ground water inflowing in the WF.

As it mentioned, many of the wells are aged and their capacities don't match an original indicators. The main reasons are:

There were analyzed CCTV results for 43 water wells from Chupanata WF and mostly there were clogged by solid deposits, corrosion products and small pieces of the sand (from aquifer). By detailed investigation 23 of them were recommended to clean or rehabilitate by different methods. Other 20 were decided to conserve or to tamponage. The global ecological problem as the Aral Sea disaster makes it more urgent not only for one nation but also for the all Central Asian region. Region needs to be developed by following SDG and the same time to save water resources. There is environmentally safe and enough by quantity and also hydrologically balance of the ground water resources in the region. It is related to use huge number of the water wells as artesian and also drainage wells. Increasing the number of the population and industrial enterprises as consumers leads to increasing in their demand for water and, accordingly, the number, capacity and costs of water wells increase. In order to supply by water of consumers, in most cases, additional wells are built, the cost of which is much higher than prolongation of the old ones. This article is devoted to the water wells inspection technology by using more modern devices and methods following SDGs in the region of Uzbekistan. Operation of the water wells in the condition of poor groundwater quality, in high water rigidity and climate change are the most causes for the result of the salt depositions, filter corrosion in the pores and on the surface of the water well filters as well as near filter zones. It leads to decreasing in the productivity of wells. At the UZWATER National center of SamSACU researches and investigations of clogging deposits as the chemically and mineralogically multicomponent complex composition particles. Which is the main reason for reducing of productivity of the water wells. Also developed effective and environmentally safe water wells' rehabilitation technology by using complex reagents as organophosphoric acids which helps to remove of the clogging deposits and to stable filtration process and work of the water wells.

Recommendations

- It is required to investigate each well by debit, specific debit and compare their indicators by passport and current capacity;
- Before giving any recommendation for further action it should be discussed with well experts, hydrogeologist and water production company representative;
- If by some serious reasons water well can't be operated it can recommend for liquidation or tamponage.
- Any decision must be justified by economic and engineering factors.

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